

Pest management and control INSECTS

Transmission of rice yellow dwarf with the blue race of *Nephotettix virescens*

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During investigations on the transmission of rice yellow dwarf by the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*, a few blue-colored adults were observed in the

rearing cages. These adults were separated and reared separately on healthy rice seedlings enclosed in clear-plastic cages. In the first generation the progeny segregated into blue and green colors. In subsequent generations, only blue leafhoppers appeared.

The transmission efficiency of rice yellow dwarf by blue- and green-colored *N. virescens* was tested. Second-instar nymphs of both blue and green *N. virescens* were collected and released separately on plants infected with rice

yellow dwarf for 24 hours of acquisition feeding. After a 30-day incubation period in the leafhoppers, 25 female and 25 male adults from each group were enclosed individually with 15-day-old healthy plants of the rice cultivar IET2295 for 48 hours. The percentage of active transmitters was 64% for blue females, 48% for blue males, 56% for green females, and 44% for green males. Therefore the blue race of *N. virescens* was as good a transmitter of yellow dwarf as the common green race. ■

Effectiveness of seedling root dip for control of gall midge

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Early planting or the use of gall midge-resistant (GMR) varieties helps reduce rice gall midge damage. When farmers are not prepared to grow GMR varieties and also must plant late, chemicals (granular systemic insecticides) are the only available means of protection. But most chemicals are too costly for the average farmer.

A seedling root dip, if effective, should be economical. Although prophylactic in nature, it would fit into a system of integrated pest control because of its low cost and its ecological selectivity (seedling dip would have little adverse effect on natural enemies of gall midge).

In our preliminary pesticide screening trials, we found the insecticides chlorpyrifos and isofenphos promising for use in seedling root-dip treatment (Table 1).

In another experiment, we further tested those insecticides in both plain water and a 1% urea solution. The dipping time of 1 hour was extended to 3 hours.

The dipping in 0.02% isofenphos for 12 hours was most effective (Table 2). But when isofenphos was used with 1.0% urea, reduction of the dipping time

Table 1. Percentages of silver shoots, productive tillers, and sound grains and average yield of rice variety Jaya under different seedling root dip treatments to control rice gall midge. Raipur, India.^a

Treatment	Dipping time (h)	Silver shoots (%) at 30 DT ^b	Productive tillers (%) at harvest ^c	Sound grains (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Untreated check		47.4 c	45.7 e	62.4	1.8 de
Isofenphos 0.02% in water	12	39.0 bcde	56.1 abcd	66.3	2.6 bc
Isofenphos 0.02% in water	1	40.0 cde	46.8 d	67.8	1.9 cde
Isofenphos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	12	35.4 bcd	48.4 d	63.4	2.3 bcd
Isofenphos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	1	29.7 ab	52.6 cd	60.5	2.6 b
Isofenphos 0.04% in water	12	23.3 a	64.6 a	57.1	3.5 a
Isofenphos 0.04% in water	1	41.9 de	48.3 d	63.0	1.5 e
Isofenphos 0.04% in 1% urea solution	12	29.8 abc	54.8 abcd	61.4	2.2 bcd
Isofenphos 0.04% in 1% urea solution	1	32.8 abcd	63.4 ab	61.1	2.2 bcd
Chlorpyrifos 0.02% in water	12	33.8 bcd	60.2 abc	61.6	2.3 bcd
Chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	12	35.9 bcd	50.7 cd	64.3 ns	2.1 bcd

^aIn a column, any 2 means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level. ns = not significant. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cAngular transformed value.

Table 2. Percentages of silver shoots, productive tillers, and sound grains and average yield of rice variety Jaya under different seedling root dip treatments^a to control rice gall midge. Raipur, India.

Treatment	Dipping time (h)	Silver shoots (%) at 30 DT ^b	Productive tillers (%) at harvest ^c	Sound grains (%)	Av yield (t/ha)
Isofenphos 0.02%	12	14.5 a	70.1	67.6	2.2 a
Isofenphos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	3	15.3 a	59.9	70.1	1.8 ab
Chlorpyrifos 0.02%	12	20.8 b	62.6	67.5	1.5 bc
Chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution	3	14.4 a	59.8	67.2	1.4 bc
Untreated check		36.6 a	59.9 ns	64.78 ns	1.2 c

^aIn a column, any 2 means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level. ns = not significant. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cAngular transformed values.